

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter* (IRRN) request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference with abbreviation in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were ... *or* Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common – not trade – names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Prevention of lodging in rice plants during rapid generation advance

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The maintenance of high nitrogen levels at the seedling stage is imperative for hastening flowering time during rapid generation advance (RGA). Dense spacing is needed to accommodate large numbers of segregating plants during RGA. The high nitrogen level and dense spacing conditions cause the breeding materials to become tall and to lodge as early as 3 weeks after planting. This creates inconvenience in raising the materials. Some plants may die unless

some leaf pruning is done, additional support is provided, or a chemical is sprayed to prevent plant elongation.

The tests we conducted showed that pruning the plants at 15 cm above the ground 22 days after sowing prevented the plants from becoming too tall but did not significantly delay flowering.

During pruning, one could also inoculate the plants for bacterial blight by the clipping technique.

Premature lodging can also be minimized by spraying B995 at 4,000 ppm on 35-day-old seedlings. Plant height can be reduced by as much as 40%, depending on the variety or line.

Another way of preventing lodging in plants growing in the RGA carts is to provide metal posts at each corner. The posts should have holes for strings that can help support the plants. ■

Submergence-tolerance screening of rice during rapid generation advance

S. K. Bardhan Roy, J. Peralta, and B. S. Vergara, Plant Physiology Department, International Rice Research Institute

In rainfed wetland rice culture, total submergence of the rice plant is common, especially just after transplanting. Varieties for this situation need submergence tolerance. It has been shown that varietal differences in submergence tolerance exist and that screening for the trait at the seedling stage is easy.

In rainfed wetland rice where photoperiod-sensitive varieties may be required, the breeding process is accelerated through rapid generation advance (RGA). A study investigated the possibility of screening for submergence tolerance during the RGA process crosses for rainfed wetland rice. The efficiency of two types of containers was also tested. Presoaked seeds of 9 susceptible and resistant varieties were

sown in vials (3.0 cm diam, 4.5 cm high) and in square pots (5.2 cm diam, 5.0 cm high). Each vial or pot contained a single plant, and was replicated three times. Plants were submerged 10 days after sowing for 7 days and percentage of survival of each variety was recorded 7 days after treatment.

The known submergence-tolerant varieties FR 13A, Thavalu 15314, Kurkaruppan, and Thavalu 15325 did not differ in survival ability in the two containers. Susceptible varieties like IR42, IR38, IR8 showed different results but equally poor survival. The mean survival percentage of all varieties is greater in vials than in square pots, but the difference is not statistically significant.

Thus, vials can be used instead of square pots in tests for submergence tolerance. The vials will save space, but the green pots have a larger volume of soil and provide larger panicles. If screening is at F₄, more seeds may be required and a larger container like the

Survival of 9 rice varieties in 2 types of containers submerged for 7 days at seedling stage. IRRI, 1980.

Variety	Mean percentage of survival	
	Vial	Square pot
Thavalu 15314	100	100
Thavalu 15325	100	100
Kurkaruppan	100	96
FR13A	100	90
KDML105	50	40
SML Temerin	38	23
IR8	38	80
IR42	50	16
IR38	17	30
Mean	66	64

“t” calculated value = 0.2927 ns at df. 8.

square pots may be necessary.

The study shows that screening for submergence tolerance at seedling stage during RGA is possible. Elimination of most of the susceptible lines will decrease the RGA population and increase the chances of the remaining lines to survive submergence under field conditions. ■

Selection for earliness or short growth duration during rapid generation advance in rice breeding

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Delayed heading or long growth duration is a major effect of low temperature on rice plants. When temperature is low, delayed panicle initiation, which may result from long growth duration, causes degeneration of spikelets and sterility. Flowering of rice plants in low temperatures causes sterility.

A 130-day cultivar in the tropics may have a growth duration of 200 days in low-temperature areas. To have a duration of 130-150 days in those areas, it should mature only within 90-100 days in the lowland tropics. Earliness is therefore one of the main criteria used for selection in improving cultivars for the low-temperature areas.

In an experiment to determine if selection for earliness is possible during the rapid generation advance (RGA) and in what generation it is feasible, the seeds

of two crosses — IR20654 (K78-13/IR5908-125-1) and IR22553 (Fujisaka 5/Knl B-361-8-6-9) — were sown in plastic pots (5.2 cm diam × 5.0 cm high) filled with soil and added fertilizer. Flowering dates for both F₂ and F₃ plants were noted.

Selection of F₂ plants that flowered in 70 days or less resulted in a 31% reduction of the population for IR22553 and 12% for IR20654. The reduction in population greatly facilitated the handling of the materials and provided space for more plants. However, in the IR22553 cross, 28% of the short-growth-duration lines (< 70 days) in the F₃ were eliminated when selection for earliness was made in F₂ plants. Similarly, 15% in

IR20654 were lost. In a large F₂ population, an average loss of 21% may be permissible.

Of the F₃ population that resulted from selection for earliness in F₂ of the cross IR22553 (< 70 days), 72% had a growth duration of less than 70 days. The value for IR20654 was 84%. These high values justify early selection (at F₂) for earliness (see table).

Selection for earliness, however, does not involve cold tolerance at seedling stage. If selection for earliness is made at F₂, a population of around 2,000 plants should be the minimum so that F₃ selection for cold tolerance at seedling stage could be conducted. ■

Heading days of 2 crosses in 2 generations under rapid generation advance.

F ₃	IR22553 F ₂ plants (no.)		F ₃	IR20654 F ₂ plants (no.)	
	51-70 d	71-90 d		51-70 d	71-108 d
41-70d	316	120	51-70 d	623	111
71-100 d	21	28	71-80 d	114	51

Problems and prospects of rice in Manipur

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Rice is the principal crop of the State of Manipur in the northeast corner of India. The State comprises an area of 22,356 km² and lies between 23.50° and 25.41° N latitude and 93° and 94.45° E longitude. The State is hilly and undulating except for the valley portion of about 2,235 km². The elevation of the valley is about 765-890 m; in the hills, the altitude ranges from 900 to 3,010 m. The climate is subtropical with assured rainfall, but temperature and other meteorologic conditions vary. Maximum temperatures of about 32° C in the valley and 27° C in the hills are registered in June-July. Minimum temperatures of about 1.5° C in the plains to 0° C in the hills are registered in December-January. Average annual rainfall varies from 1,350 mm in the valley to 1,800 mm in the

hills. The dry season from December to March has little rainfall.

An area of 172,000 ha under rice cultivation yields an average of 1.5 t/ha. In the valley rice, mostly transplanted, is grown in low-lying areas. Rice is also the main crop in the hills. Farmers in the north and northeast practice terraced cultivation. Transplanting normally is from mid-June to late July. Harvest is from late October to late November. All these operations are 15 to 20 days early in the hills. More than 80% of the area is planted to local glutinous varieties such as Moirangphou, Phoudum, Kakchingphou, and Langmanbi — preferred by the local population.

Over the last decade the Department of Agriculture has had limited success in introducing some high-yielding, short-duration, photoperiod-insensitive varieties such as IR8, Jaya, Ratna, and Palaman. IR24 is becoming popular because of its high yield and low amylose character, but it is very susceptible to blast, a disease that is favored by weather conditions in Manipur. With the development of